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DEVELOPMENT OF MECHATRONIC-SYSTEM-EMBEDDED WOODEN TOYS BASED ON HOKKAIDO REGIONAL ORIGINALITIES

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we proposed value-added products by embedding mechatronic systems into the inside of traditional toys based on Hokkaido regional originalities. These toys were constructed of 'ezomatsu' (*Picea jezoensis*) wood, one of the most typical woods which has been approved as a 'Tree of Hokkaido' from 1966. We described two mechatronic-system-embedded wooden toys applied the 'ezomatsu' materials for these appearances. The one was an interactive 'tsumiki' (building blocks) toy that appeals to players reacting with their block operations, and the other was a woodcraft based robot toy in the motif of a Blakiston's fish owl, called 'Kotan Kor Kamui', a household god of the Ainu. We then showed the development of effective prototypes of each toy, including mechatronic systems embedded in these toys.

Keywords: mechatronics, wooden toy, interaction

INTRODUCTION

Hokkaido is one of the high quality wood production areas in Japan, and the 'ezomatsu' (*Picea jezoensis*) is the most typical wood which has been approved as a 'Tree of Hokkaido' from 1966. There are many wood craft works and traditional toys such as 'tsumiki' (building blocks), 'garagara' (rattle), and 'mamagoto' (play mother) tools all over the 'ezomatsu' production areas. We can also find a lot of wood sculptures in the motif of local animals as classic souvenirs. Especially, several activities are in operation to review the worth of wood materials: 'chizai-chisyo' meaning that consuming wood

materials and its products in its produced regions (The website of 'chizai-chisyo'), and 'moku-iku' meaning that education of wood materials to learn its good features and signification of wood utilization for the purpose of making civilian and children familiar with wood culture (The project report of 'moku-iku').

In this study, we proposed value-added products by embedding mechatronic systems into the inside of traditional toys. We described two mechatronic-system-embedded wooden toys applied the 'ezomatsu' materials for these appearances. This material has good features such as light weight, the robustness against temperature and vapor, easily fabricated, and good appearance because of straight wood grain. We also incorporated 'tsumiki (building blocks)' playing into our design concept. The traditional 'tsumiki' toy has potentials to nurture children's thoughts and intellectual development (Motoko Ohfuji, 2007, and Haruyo Fujisaki & Takashi Muto, 1985), and to cultivate children's emotions because of characteristics of the natural materials (Yoshihiro Obata, et al., 2002).

As mechatronic systems are introduced into toys, various mechatronic toys have been inspired by the concept of 'tsumiki' to improve its creativity and intellectual ability. This is especially true for LEGO products, which fuse two components: the 'tsumiki' concept of bricks, and mechatronics for LEGO Mindstorms NXT systems (The website of LEGO). This system consists of a microprocessor embedded NXT block, sensors, motors, lump blocks, and original LEGO blocks. The users can construct an original effective robot assembling these parts intentionally, and can give a motion order coded by software via USB interface.

The Topobo (Hayes Solos Raffle et al., 2004), produced by Prof. Ishii and his laboratory, has a kinetic memory, which can record and replay its physical motion. This toy consists of actives and passives. The actives, egg-shaped plastic objects, are robotic nodes with kinetic memory, and the passives, nine different shapes, can be used to build a variety of physical structures. Constructing these parts, the Topobo is intended to model various figures.

The Fischertechnik (The website of Fischertechnik), born in German, is a block kit specialized in constructing structure, because it includes rigid blocks and more than 450 mechanical parts such as gear, screw, and pulley. All parts can connect each other solidly, and also a variety of stable structure models can be built according to player's intension. In all these mechatronic toys, engineering plastics are applied for the appearance and structures. These plastic materials have many good characteristics making them suitable for mass production, including being light in weight and having high degrees of stiffness and hardness. But they have several drawbacks, for example, uniform texture without a tactile feeling of warmth and a lack of bulk (Kunio Maeda, 1988).

Consequently, these 'tsumiki' inspired toys are focused on intellectual functions of 'tsumiki', but sensitivity of wood material has not been used effectively.

We described two mechatronic-system-embedded wooden toys applied the 'ezomatsu' materials for these appearances. The one was an interactive 'tsumiki' (building blocks) toy which appeals to players reacting with their block operations, and the other was a woodcraft based robot toy in the motif of a Blakiston's fish owl, called 'Kotan Kor Kamui', a household god of the Ainu. We then showed the development of effective prototypes of each toy, including mechatronic systems embedded in these toys. In their toys, good tactile of the wooden appearance encourages children's repetitive play, which leads affection to these toys, that is, good features of wood material and appetite for learning of local animals applied as the motif of appearance.

PROTOTYPE OF INTERACTIVE 'TSUMIKI' TOY

The 'tsumiki' toy consists of wooden blocks of various shapes, including cube, pyramid, and cylinder. These blocks can be assembled, built, stacked, lined, or handled, in any way the player intends. Mechatronic systems in each block are embedded so that these natural playing actions cause switch signals. For example, when two blocks, the magnet-embedded and the magnet- sensor-embedded blocks are stacked, this action works a switch, the combinations of LED-embedded and CdS-brightness-sensor-embedded blocks can also be worked as a switch, and also using a tilt sensor, the block rotation can be dealt as a switch. In addition, part inserting action performs a switch using a touch sensor.

APPEARANCE

Figure 1 shows a prototype of 'tsumiki' block consist of 'ezomatsu' material. The appearance of this prototype is cubic shape, which is the most general in the 'tsumiki' blocks, and its size is 48 mm on a side, decided in reference to a commercially available 'tsumiki' block. This cube is composed of two cuboids with 24 x 48 x 48 mm in size for the purpose of embedding the mechatronics components inside. These two cuboids are joined one another using screws. There are mechatronic devices for interaction behind several holes at the center of sides.

Figure 1. Appearance of 'tsumiki' block prototype consist of 'ezomatsu' material

MECHATRONICS COMPONENTS

As shown in Figure 2, the mechatronics system embedded in a 'tsumiki' block consists of a PIC16F819 processor, a CdS brightness sensor, a magnetic sensor, tilt switch, four LEDs, and two CR2016 lithium coin batteries for power supply. Each side of the cube has various functions according to the concealed mechatronics devices. There is a hole at the center of some sides of the cube, which allow to input light to the CdS sensor or to output light irradiated from a LED. The lighting pattern of four LEDs is changed by the ON/OFF condition of sensors according to a program installed in the PIC processor. By using these functions, we can obtain interactive 'tsumiki' actions as follows:

- (1) lighting pattern changes when a player rolls over the 'tsumiki',
- (2) LEDs turn on when a magnet-embedded block or a magnet itself is stacked, and
- (3) light is emitted from the other hole when irradiating the CdS sensor behind a hole.

Figure 2. Circuit block diagram of the mechatronics system embedded in the 'tsumiki' block: Each number indicates resistance value (unit:ohm) .

DEVELOPMENT OF MECHATRONICS SYSTEM

We developed a small mechatronics system enough to embed in the 'tsumiki' block shown in Figure 1, while all devices mentioned above are mounted. This mechatronics system is composed of the sensor substrate (Figure 3) and the processor substrate (Figure 4). The battery box is settled in the front side of the sensor substrate in addition to three

sensors. An IC socket for PIC16F819, four LEDs, and resistors are built in the processor substrate. There are two LEDs extended by wires so that they can be set to each appropriate position. Two substrates communicate each other via PCB connectors.

Figure 3. Sensor substrate

Figure 4. Processor substrate

Figure 5. Overview of the mechatronics system: This is composed of two substrates.

Assembling two substrates, we obtained the mechatronics system shown in Figure 5. The size of the mechatronics system is about 30 x 22 x 15 mm, and the maximum height is 38 mm including the CR2016 lithium coin batteries. This means that it is possible to ensure at least 5 mm in wall thickness of all sides of the 'tsumiki' block.

INTERNAL STRUCTURE OF 'TSUMIKI' BLOCK

The 'tsumiki' block is composed of two cuboids which are hollowed so that the mechatronics system can be embedded in them (Figure 6(a) and (b)). They were fabricated by a 3D rapid prototyping machine tool, MDX-40A (Roland DG Corporation). Using the SolidWorks 3D-CAD software, we designed these hollows according to the shape of the mechatronics system. As shown in Figure 7, the mechatronics system fits the hollowed top part. Then building the bottom parts, we obtain a prototype of interactive 'tsumiki' block.

(a) top

(b) bottom

Figure 6. The hollowed cuboids

SUMMARY AND PROJECTED WORKS

The prototype of interactive 'tsumiki' block introduced in this section is a work-in-progress. We need more brushing up to obtain a complete one. At the next step, we will test by the target user of children from 3 to 6 years old, then check the size of 'tsumiki' block, the effectiveness of interactive elements on children's creativities and concentration. In addition, the mechatronics system should be improved. This system is driven by two lithium coin batteries. When running out, they need to be replaced, after the 'tsumiki' block is taken apart using a screw driver, which brings players or their parents bother. The lithium coin batteries also have a risk for being swallowed by children. We are planning to apply rechargeable battery with wireless charging. Then a charge box will be prepared so that the 'tsumiki' blocks are recharged when they are stored in this box. This suggests the training for well-organization. Moreover, sound and vibration components will be included in the next revision of the mechatronics system.

To advance the sensuousness of appearance, we will try to apply mortise-tenon joint instead of screws for the connection of two cuboids. Especially, when the rechargeable battery would be applied, assembled cuboids need to be taken apart no more. We project to develop the other shape 'tsumiki' blocks such as triangle, cylinder, parallelogram, et al, and also project to apply other wood materials produced in Hokkaido, for example, 'enju' (*styphonolobium japonicum*), 'nara' (*quercus mongolica* var. *grosseserrata*), 'Ichii' (*taus cuspidata*), et al.

Figure 7. Top part that the mechatronics parts are embedded

PROTOTYPE ROBOT OF BLAKISTON'S FISH OWL, CALLED 'KOTAN KOR KAMUI', A HOUSEHOLD GOD OF THE AINU

We can find a lot of wood craft works in the motif of local animals and aquatic animals, for example, *ursus arctos yesoensis*, *sciurus vulgaris orientis*, *vulpes vulpes schrencki*, *clione*, *oncorhynchus mykiss*, and so on, in souvenir shops. Especially, Blakiston's fish owl (Figure 8) is one of the most symbolic animal in Hokkaido, because it is the largest owl in Japan, about 70-centimeters long and large wings with a wingspan of 1.8-meters, and also called a 'Kotan Kor Kamui,' a household god of the Ainu people. It inhabits around liver, lake and spring in the northeastern area of Hokkaido. Because there are only 120 individuals remaining according to forest destruction and environmental contamination, this owl has been designated as an endangered species.

Figure 8. Blakiston's fish owl, also called 'Kotan Kor Kamui', a household god of the Ainu people

DESIGN CONCEPT

The concept of robot design is 'coexistence of ferociousness and winsomeness' of Blakiston's fish owl. When finding a fish, a staple food for this owl, on a perch, it goes flying straight at the catch, with blinking its eyes and clapping its wings. We feel loveliness in its figure on a perch, and also we feel ferociousness in hunting motion. In this study, we expressed this winsomeness in the figure, and this ferociousness in motions using the mechatronic systems.

'TSUMIKI' AS A DESIGN ELEMENTS

In designing this robot toy, we incorporated 'tsumiki' toy into our design element. That is, this robot toy consists of several parts. When these are assembled

in a defined manner, for example, building (Figure 9(a)) and inserting (Figure 9(b)), this robot toy starts to move. In this study, a mechatronic system is embedded so that part inserting action performs a switch for the robot motion as shown in Figure 9(b).

Figure 9. The 'tsumiki' action as a switch of the robot motion

MECHATRONICS SYSTEM TO EXPRESS THE OWL MOTIONS

As shown in Figure 10, three mechatronics devices are mounted in order to express the owl motions: two LEDs to make the eyes twinkle, a speaker to make the owl hoot, and a servo motor to enable the owl to flap. And four switches can be connected to detect player's actions.

Figure 10. Circuit block diagram of the mechatronics system for The Robot of Blakiston's fish owl

APPEARANCE DESIGN

At the appearance design of the robot toy, we observed a Blakiston's fish owl and then obtained four characteristics: (1) glaring eyes, (2) ear tufts, (3) pointed beak, and (4) large wings. After making sketches of this owl focusing on these characteristics, we built a Styrofoam model manufactured using cutters and sandpapers (Figure 11). Then we constructed a hard mockup of this owl using the 'ezomatsu' wood material (Figure 12) to evaluate its weight, appearance, and the shape of each part. This mockup was composed of five parts. All wooden parts were fabricated using a band saw for crude processing, an electric sander for overall shaping, and fine abrasive sandpaper for finishing, until each made good tactile impression. We applied yellow colored acrylic parts with black seal to the face to simulate large eyes. The edges of the beak part were rounded, while retaining its sharpness. Similarly, the ear tufts were distended for emphasis. The growth rings of the wooden pieces were used to enhance the appearance of each part. Especially in the body and wing parts, the directions of the growth rings were adjusted to those of the feather patterns of a Blakiston's fish owl.

(a) overview

(b) wing flapping

Figure 11. A Styrofoam study model

(a) front view

(b) side view

Figure 12. A hard mockup using the 'ezomatsu' materials

DEVELOPMENT OF EFFECTIVE ROBOT

Based on the hard mockup mentioned above, we developed an effective robot toy shown in Figure 13. The robot body is composed of the front (Figure 14) and the backward (Figure 15). Assembly of the two parts resulted in three cavities: a 130 x 35 x 30 mm cavity for an electronic circuit substrate and two 40 x 22 x 14 mm cavities for the MICRO/2BBMG (GWS) servo motors, one directly connected to each wing part (Figure 16). The face, composed of yellow colored acrylic parts and a beak part (Figure 17), was mounted onto the front part of the body. An orange colored LED was inserted behind each acrylic part, to simulate eye twinkling. Power was supplied by an AC-DC adaptor with a rated constant voltage of 5V and a maximum current of 2 A.

The electronic circuit substrate described in Figure 18, called the 'main board', was 34 x 72 mm in size and was reduced from the ICB-86 universal substrate (Sunhayato) to fit the size of the cavity. The function

of the main board was assembled so as to realize motions of the robot toy prototype. In this prototype, two motions, wing clap and eye twinkling were integrated, so a speaker and its peripheral electronic parts with cables have been omitted. Two orange LEDs were drawn out using cables from connectors on the substrate to the face part. Also, each servo motor was connected to the substrate with three cables: voltage source, ground, and signal. These servo motors are driven by pulse-width modulation (PWM) signals. Thus, each signal cable from two servo motors is linked to a #9 pin in the PIC16F819, with the pin used as the PWM mode. Several connectors were attached so that signal cables from sensor and switch devices can insert as necessary.

Figure 15. Backward part of the robot body with the main circuit board (unit: mm)

Figure 13. Overview of an effective robot prototype (unit: mm)

Figure 16. Wing part with a servo motor (unit: mm)

Figure 14. Front part of the robot body (unit: mm)

Figure 17. Face part composed of ear tuft, beak, acrylic eyes, and LEDs (unit: mm)

Figure 18. Main circuit board of the mechatronics system (unit: mm)

Figure 19. Cylindrical sticks for switching with player's inserting actions (unit: mm)

Figure 20. Switch circuit board (unit: mm)

A 'tsumiki' element was incorporated into the prototype, according to the inserting concept shown in Figure 9(b). We constructed cylindrical sticks (Figure 19) to be inserted into three holes in the front part of the body. We then installed a mechanism allowing the robot toy to perform various actions when the cylindrical sticks are inserted into their holes. We attached a tact switching device at the right below of each hole, with each of these

switching devices mounted onto another substrate, the 'switch board' (Figure 20). This switch board was connected to the main board through pin connectors. Consequently, each tact switching device was placed just under the corresponding hole on the front part of body and was pushed when a cylindrical stick was inserted (Figure 21).

All parts of the robot toy were subsequently assembled (Figure 22). This toy is controlled by a PIC16F819 microprocessor, which determines which tact switching device has been pushed and then outputs signals to the mechatronic devices. In this prototype, we programmed three motions in accordance with the number of switches (Table 1). We show here the actual motions of this prototype (Figure 23).

Figure 21. Positional relationship among tact switch, hole, and stick: each tact switch is right below a hole, and then is pushed when a stick is inserted into a hole

Figure 22. Composition of the robot toy

switch	motion
left	eyes twinkling slowly
center	wings flapping
right	eyes twinkling quickly

Table 1. Motions corresponding to each switch

EVALUATIONS

We demonstrated this prototype at the 56th Annual Conference of the Japanese Society for the Science of Design (JSSD), and at the Japan Society of Mechanical Engineers (JSME) Robotics and Mechatronics Conference 2010, and we obtained several evaluations from participants at these academic conferences. The appearance and tactile properties of the prototype were reviewed favorably. People who evaluated the mechanism of the robot toy were interested in several of the mechanical features. For example, the electronic circuit substrate was minimized to fit into the internal space of the robot body; the internal mechanism and cables were invisible, omitting the use of an AC-DC adaptor; and motion occurs immediately after inserting a cylindrical stick. Incorporating the 'tsumiki' elements as a switch indicated that this concept has the potential to be a novel type of man-machine interface. Individuals who examined the prototype toy at these conferences, however, also pointed out that the movement of the wing, using a rotational degree of freedom, differs from the actual wing flap of a Blakiston's fish owl; that the shape of the wings in the model is quite different from the shape of real wings; that there is no power on/off switch; and that the position of the power supply jack was inadequate. In addition, when we later examined our prototype, we noted that several improvements could be incorporated: the electronic circuit substrate could be optimized as a printed-circuit board; additional motions could be added; other, smaller actuators are needed to better design the robot body because large actuators limit its size and shape. Moreover, 'tsumiki' elements should be incorporated so as not to interfere with the actual image of the animal. For the study of usability examinations for the targeted children of this toy, we consulted a professor belonging to the children nursing course, School of Nursing, Sapporo City University, who is a member of the university ethics

(a) wing flapping

(b) eyes blinking

Figure 23. Motions of the robot toy

committee. Then we obtained advice that this prototype was unsuited for the examinations, because there are unnecessary holes and gaps, and also the power strip of AC-DC adaptor is pulled easily, which provokes distraction of examinees. If these problems are not improved, we could not obtain effective results of examinations.

SUMMARY AND PROJECTED WORKS

In summary, we have defined the design concept of a proposed robot toy and constructed a study model, a mockup, and an effective prototype in a series of design processes. The effective prototype did not incorporate voice expression by a speaker, but did incorporate wing motion by servo motors and eye twinkling by LEDs. Thus, while we were able to incorporate some of the characteristics of a Blakiston's fish owl, we could not incorporate all relevant characteristics. The 'tsumiki' elements should be incorporated in such a way as to reflect the animal's behavior and ecology.

In developing a second prototype, we will attempt to:

- load a sound chip and a speaker to enable vocalization by the toy,
- improve the appearance of each body part so that it is close to that of the real animal,
- examine the use of other actuators, including artificial muscle actuators, DC motors, and piezoelectric actuators,
- design a mechanism to achieve realistic wing flapping with as few actuators as possible,
- incorporate the 'tsumiki' elements so as to mimic the predatory activity of the Blakiston's fish owl, and
- develop a high-quality finished model capable of the usability examinations for the targeted users.

CONCLUSION

We introduced two prototypes of mechatronic-system-embedded wooden toys. In the future, we will improve them and then we will conduct experiments of examinee to evaluate children's immersions to these toys. These toys are targeted at children from 4- to 12-year-old, who plays these toys in kindergarten or in home. Especially, senior children at elementary school start to learn the foundations of mechatronics such as physics and electricity.

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